

Improved Performance of Polyhedral Oligomeric Silsesquioxane Epoxies

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Abstract: In high voltage applications, polymer insulation can be exposed to very high electrical field stress, resulting in long term exposure to corona. The electrical field stress may be much below dielectric breakdown threshold. Eventually the exposure to corona can lead to failure of the high voltage component. Nanometer sized inorganic fillers are increasingly used as reinforcing materials for mechanical or thermal property improvement of polymers. Improvements in mechanical modulus or heat deflection temperature are often realized. These fillers may also improve some electrical properties such as corona endurance in polymers. In the current study, polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) loaded epoxies were produced and tested for corona endurance. Results suggest a five times improvement in ac corona lifetime of selected POSS-epoxies compared to unloaded epoxy.

Introduction

Inorganic fillers for polymers are an active research area [1,2,3]. While inorganic fillers such as carbon black and silica have been used for decades in rubber polymers, new synthesis methods have yielded nanosized inorganic fillers for a variety of polymers resulting in improved system properties. These nanosized inorganic fillers may offer improved properties due to size uniformity, interfacial characteristics, and nonagglomeration performance. Mechanical and thermal properties have been investigated for a number of hybrids. Besides mechanical and thermal properties some electrical properties have been investigated for these hybrids. In a corona resistance study, Henk et. al. found an over nine times increased corona resistance with a 4.7% by volume loading of nanometer sized silica particles in an epoxy when compared to the pure epoxy [4]. Nelson and Fothergill found an increase in electric strength of an epoxy by adding titanium dioxide nanoparticles [5].

In this work corona resistance is investigated for a control epoxy and a 5% by weight POSS loaded epoxy. Additional measurements using infrared spectroscopy and dynamic mechanical analysis were done to garner information for possible performance explanations.

Surface FTIR measurements were done on unexposed and corona exposed POSS-epoxy specimens to determine if a silicon rich passivating layer may form on the sample surface. In an atomic oxygen exposure experiment by Phillips et. al., a silicon rich passivating layer formed in a POSS-polymer [6].

Corona resistance was chosen as a performance metric for three reasons. As previously mentioned, corona attack is a deleterious mechanism for many polymer insulated high voltage components. Second, a POSS loaded polymer has already shown superior erosion performance to atomic oxygen which is by definition a free radical [6]. Third, a POSS-polypropylene has shown a seven times increase in corona lifetime when compared to a control polypropylene [7].

Experimental Method

An epoxy resin from Resolution Performance Products was used (EPON 828). The curing agent was an aliphatic diamine (Jeffamine D400). All samples were cured for two hours at 80°C and then three hours at 125°C. Corona lifetime samples averaged 0.17 mm in thickness. The structure of the particular POSS used, (trisilanolphenyl-POSS obtained from Hybrid Plastics), is shown in Figure 1.

The corona endurance tests were performed with ASTM and IEC suggested electrodes [8,9]. Each rod electrode was 6 mm in diameter with a 1 mm radius at the tip edge. The plane electrode was sized to include all of the discharge area. The rod electrode was placed on the surface of the sample with a 30 gram mass per ASTM D 2275-89. A 3 kV rms voltage was applied at a frequency of 60 Hertz. For the IR measurements, attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) microspectroscopy was done using a BioRad FTS-3000/UMA500 instrument. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was done with a TA Instruments DMA 2980 in 3 point bending mode at 1 Hz and 2°C/min in air. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed with a TA Instruments Q1000 at 5°C/min.

Figure 1: Trisilanolphenyl-POSS structure used in experiment.

Results and Discussion

Five percent POSS loaded epoxy showed a five times increase in corona endurance over the epoxy without POSS (Figure 2). Average time to failure for the control epoxy was 65.7 hours. Average time to failure for the POSS-epoxy was 330.8 hours. DMA results showed a 3.6 degree increase in the glass transition temperature (T_g) and a fifteen percent increase in the storage modulus of the five percent POSS loaded epoxy over the control epoxy. DSC results indicated an increase in T_g of 2.6°C for the POSS-epoxy samples compared to the neat resin (see Table 1).

Figure 2: Time to failure of three control epoxy and three POSS-Epoxy samples tested at 3 kV rms

Table 1: Thermal analysis results.

	DMA		DSC
	E' (GPa)	T_g^1	T_g
Neat epoxy	2.14	49.0°C	44.0°C
5% POSS	2.51	52.6°C	46.6°C

¹ T_g taken from E'' peak

Surface FTIR spectra were done on unexposed and corona-exposed five percent POSS loaded epoxy. The unexposed POSS-epoxy showed characteristic absorbances for Si-O (~1100 cm^{-1}), C-O (~1246 cm^{-1}), C-H (~2870-2970 cm^{-1}), and O-H (~3400 cm^{-1}), (Figure 3). The exposed sample failed after 394 hours at a voltage of three kV rms. A white visible ring developed on the sample surface around the upper electrode. The surface FTIR results suggest that a Si-O rich layer is developed at the surface near the high electric field region. Epoxy absorbances are severely diminished at wavenumbers 1246, and 2870 to 2970 in this region (Figure 4). Directly under the electrode and two cm from the center of the electrode, the spectra were very similar to Figure 3 showing a mix of POSS and epoxy. These areas were essentially away from the region influenced by the corona.

Figure 3. μ ATR-FTIR of corona unexposed POSS-epoxy.

Figure 4. μ ATR-FTIR of corona exposed POSS-epoxy after 394 hours at 3 kV rms.

Summary and Conclusions

POSS-epoxy samples showed improved corona endurance when compared to neat epoxy samples. Surface FTIR results confirm that a silicon rich layer is developed on the POSS-epoxy sample surface.

High voltage power supplies for compact electronic equipment often have premature failures. These components are often insulated with potting compounds. Failure rates are dependent upon a combination of issues: material selection, manufacturing processes, form factors, component geometries, etc. A significant factor contributing to many failures, is the presence of corona in small voids within the potting. The organic potting compounds often used in these supplies generally flow well in manufacturing, but are much more susceptible to corona than inorganic insulators such as mica. The addition of inorganic nanoparticles to epoxies shows the potential of inhibiting corona degradation.

Keeping in mind that "void-free" potting is always a high priority in such power supplies, the viscosity of the potting material is an important manufacturing consideration. Therefore viscosity measurements are a part of planned future research. Additionally, samples will be prepared with POSS particles covalently grafted to the epoxy. Such grafted materials rather than materials incorporating a physical blend of POSS in the epoxy may aid in dispersion when making large insulating structures. Finally, SEM and/or TEM will be used to assess the quality of dispersion.

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